

Digital Text Reading and Comprehension of Students Mediated by Teacher's Teaching Efficacy

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Abstract. The study aimed to investigate the mediating effect of teachers' teaching efficacy on the relationship between digital text and learners' reading comprehension, employing a non-experimental quantitative design with a descriptive-correlation technique. This study used path analysis through mediation to determine the mediating effect of teachers' teaching efficacy on the relationship between digital text and learners' reading comprehension. Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro students. The researcher considered all 130 bona fide students enrolled in the Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro schools as study respondents or samples. The Digital Text Reading in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro, was moderately extensive. Digital Text Reading, which addresses motivation, interest, and efficacy, has received extensive ratings. Digital Text Reading was complex, and Preference for Reading Digital or Print Texts obtained moderately extensive ratings. The results revealed that teachers' teaching efficacy was significantly correlated with digital text reading and reading comprehension strategies in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. Additionally, digital text reading was significantly associated with learners' reading comprehension in the Laak North District, Davao de Oro. In addition, the researcher may conduct further analysis of the factors that may contribute to the relationship between digital text reading and reading comprehension of learners, since only 30.8 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable.

KEY WORDS

1. Mediating effect
2. teachers' teaching efficacy
3. relationship
4. digital text
5. learners' reading comprehension

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1. Introduction

A fundamental ability that enhances our lives in many ways and provides access to knowledge and personal development is reading. Reading is essential to the human experience, whether for pleasure, education, or personal growth. One needs to improve reading comprehension to compete in a complex literacy environment. Reading comprehension is a complex and dynamic process, involving the reader, the text, and the act of reading itself. The rise in popularity of digital media, driven by technical improvements, has altered the way writing and reading are done. Given the significance of reading, especially reading comprehension, numerous underlying theories have been identified through extensive research to address frequent problems with low reading comprehension. On a global scale, Ali et

al. (2022) posited that technology assists both teachers and students in searching for references and other cultural content related to the literary text, ultimately having a positive impact on learning outcomes. Likewise, Bereczki Kárpáti (2021) assesses that such technology-enhanced creativity reassures experts and teachers to believe in digital technology integration. Tang et al. (2022) recommend using digital technology tools to improve students' creativity. Similarly, Giebelhausen (cited in Pardede 2019b) accentuated, "The use of digital tools as reading devices has also driven educational institutions to move to paperless classrooms worldwide. "This digital innovation has profoundly linked its purpose to the stages in Bloom's Taxonomy as questions provided appropriately arranged according to the difficulty level or in the taxonomy's hierarchy. There is also a game inserted, which was believed by Hashim et al. (2019) to engage students learning in the lesson. This study on digital comprehension expands the learner's vocabulary through verbal-linguistic intelligence. Bilonozhko and Syzenko (2020) emphasize how verbal-linguistic intelligence enables pupils to learn best from the digital content they read with purposeful technology integration. Moreover, Caena and Re-decker (2019) raise the importance of teachers being aware that they will be able to learn more as they indulge themselves in new things and find ways to adapt to the changes from then on. Conducting digital comprehension as a tool in the classroom should be treated as a practice and experience for professional development instead of acting for technology's sake. This calls for teachers to improve themselves with proper training and best pedagogy practices to deliver reading comprehension lessons effectively in the classroom. In addition, working on digital comprehension should help teachers provide alternatives to teaching reading skills. Based on the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 data, Balinbin (2020) indicated that just 29 percent of grade 5 children in the Philippines are proficient readers of a range of ordinary texts. Comparing the Philippines to Laos, which has only 2 percent of Grade 5 students who are skilled readers, the Philippines does the second poorest job at 10 percent. In addition, reading challenges were mentioned as the main reason some kids did poorly on the NAT in a 2007 interview with Dr. Yolanda Quijano, the director of the DepEd's Bureau of Elementary Education. In addition to their poor performance on state exams like the NAT, students' poor comprehension significantly contributed to their poor performance in their other academic areas (Philippine Star, 2010), as cited by Bolambao and De Vera (2018). According to the literature, the decline of long-form reading in higher education is diminishing (Baron Mangen, 2021). Digital textbooks must be accompanied by information literacy from digital technology. Digital literacy involves using technology efficiently and understanding digital content to evaluate its credibility and use appropriately (Bocar Ancheta, 2023). Locally, during the COVID-19 pandemic, a study at Bantacan National High School in New Bataan and Compostela in Davao de Oro revealed that pupils struggle with reading texts in modular remote learning. Students grow disinterested in what they have read when they cannot understand it. Because of this, students who use Modular Distance Learning find it challenging to understand their academic material—particularly those who are illiterate or slow readers. On the other hand, teaching efficacy is also one of the highlighted factors that mediate students' reading comprehension. To implement this in the classroom, teachers must be well-prepared and possess sufficient knowledge of English material and instructional methodologies for reading comprehension, preferably through hands-on activities. In light of the problems and difficulties mentioned above, the study's comparatively original approach is thus suggested. This study

aims to increase interest in the academic study of students' text comprehension problems and the never-ending quest to delve into the vast array of likely causes and circumstances surrounding such a phenomenon. Although there are extant studies on students' reading comprehension, such as a Meta-Analysis of the Effect of Paper Versus Digital Reading on Reading Comprehension in Health Professional Education by Guillaume, F. et, there are currently no studies on the effects of digital text reading on students' reading comprehension in Kapalong West District, Division of Davao del Norte. Examples of these studies include al. (2021), The Effect of Digital Texts on Primary Students' Comprehension, Fluency, and Attitude by Safak and Ihsan (2018), The Contribution of Text-highlighting to Comprehension: A Comparison of Print and Digital Reading by Ben-Yehudah, and Eshet-Alkalai (2018), and numerous others. In the Laak North District of Davao de Oro, specific educational problems further complicate the landscape. Teachers in this district face challenges related to assessment literacy—their ability to design, administer, and interpret various forms of assessments. Additionally, a notable gap in students' information comprehension skills and lack of digital text exposure hinders their academic performance and development. The district's low comprehension and lack of exposure to digital reading are a concern. Teaching efficacy has excellent potential to mediate this concern, characterized by efficacy in student engagement, efficacy in instructional strategies, and Efficacy in Classroom management. It has been identified as a potential mediator to bridge these gaps and improve educational outcomes. Moreover, our objective is to delve into the effect of digital text reading on students' reading comprehension and how teachers' teaching efficacy mediates the students' digital reading capacity. The study's findings will offer valuable insights into educational management, further enriching

the existing knowledge base on the impact of digital text reading on students' reading comprehension as mediated by teachers' teaching efficacy.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Digital Text and Reading*—Digital texts are flexible and accessible, offering customizable features such as font, color, and text-to-speech, which benefit diverse learners, especially those with disabilities (Wadi et al., 2022; Kumbhar, 2018). They allow for multimodal engagement, improve accessibility, and support differentiated instruction. However, barriers like lack of infrastructure, training, and internet access limit integration (Kumar Vijay, 2023; Wiche Ogunbodede, 2021).

Though digital platforms like Newsela personalize content and improve comprehension (Bala et al., 2023; Pinal Kshirsagar, 2020), students still face challenges in deep, focused reading due to distractions and lower engagement levels (Singer Alexander, 2017; Makebo et al., 2022). Preferences between digital and print remain mixed—while digital is efficient, print may encourage better focus and retention (Pardede, 2019; Anyim, 2020).

1.1.2. *Motivation, Reading Attitude, and Comprehension*—Motivation is a strong predictor of language learning and reading success. It impacts reading comprehension, engagement, and perseverance (Gardner Lambert, 1959; Lustyantje Aprilia, 2020; Khatee, 2020). Reading attitudes, shaped by emotions and environment, also influence comprehension. Positive experiences, particularly in early schooling, foster sustained interest, while negative ones diminish motivation over time (Akhmetova et al., 2022; Smith Li, 2020).

1.1.3. *Reading Comprehension and Instructional Strategies*—Reading comprehension requires decoding, vocabulary, background knowledge, and inferencing (Butterfuss et al., 2020; Nagy Scott, 2000). Motivation and comprehension influence each other bidirection-

ally (Toste et al., 2020). Instructional scaffolding enhances digital reading skills by gradually shifting learning responsibility to students (Azir Sriyanto, 2021). Teachers play a critical role by modeling strategies, activating prior knowledge, and guiding student engagement (Sinaga et al., 2019).

1.1.4. Teaching Efficacy and Student Engagement—Teacher self-efficacy—the belief in one’s ability to influence student learning—correlates with effective teaching, student motivation, and achievement (Lauermann ten Hagen, 2021; Mok Moore, 2019). It encompasses classroom management, instructional strategies, and student engagement (Liu et al., 2020; Goksu et al., 2022). Teachers with strong efficacy beliefs adapt better, manage classrooms effectively, and support student autonomy (Khalid Akhter, 2021; Shah, 2023).

High teacher efficacy also enhances student self-efficacy and participation. In digital contexts, it ensures the effective use of tools like annotation platforms and e-books to support differentiated learning (Nguyen et al., 2019; Frimpong Addo, 2020).

1.1.5. Digital Text and Teaching Efficacy—Effective integration of digital texts in teaching requires scaffolding, training, and adaptability. Teachers must transition from traditional to technology-enhanced strategies to remain effective in modern classrooms (Parmi, 2019). Those with higher self-efficacy are more likely to embrace such changes, which in turn improves reading comprehension outcomes among students (Banditvilai, 2020; Martina et al., 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—In today’s technology-driven world, digital literacy and reading comprehension are increasingly essential skills. They empower individuals to access, navigate, and understand information in various digital formats, enabling engagement with diverse content across multiple platforms. As digital resources proliferate, the ability to critically evaluate and synthesize information from these

sources becomes paramount. For students, utilizing text sets not only enhances content knowledge but also fosters vital language and literacy skills. These text sets provide background and contextual knowledge, facilitate connections between texts, and strengthen reading comprehension. Strong comprehension is essential for purposeful reading; it allows readers to engage meaningfully with texts, learn from them, and enjoy the reading experience. Moreover, teacher efficacy plays a vital role in the learning process. It reflects a teacher’s confidence in their ability to positively influence student learning. When teachers believe in their effectiveness, they are more inclined to set high expectations, adopt innovative strategies, and persist through challenges. This heightened sense of efficacy contributes to more dynamic classroom practices and, as a result, improves student outcomes.

1.3. Theoretical Framework—Hypertext Theory guided this study; according to Hawkes et al. (2001), the term “hypertext” employed in the second theory refers to text made up of word or image blocks electronically connected by several pathways, chains or trails. This definition highlights a significant characteristic of hypertext: its ability to link conceptually different parts of a document or entirely other texts. In contrast to printed texts, which are organized in a rigid order that readers must adhere to, hypertext dramatically enhances readers’ autonomy. Crawford (2020) considered the theoretical framework as a portion of the conceptual framework (CF) theory in the context of research, particularly within social sciences, which examined the linkages in the study in the context of creating additional theories or testing existing theories. Consequently, the theoretical framework provides the researcher with a level playground for conveying his/ her research focus/ thought from the abstract to background to the study to the literature review, to data gathering and analysis, to the interpretation and discussion of findings, to ascertaining whether or

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the study

not the study objective have been achieved and identified problem, solved initially, to the summary, to drawing conclusions and making recommendations, to contributions to the body of existing knowledge, to suggesting further studies in the area and each of these aspects are linked with one another. Also, Several studies have reported significant gains in PSTs' academic achievements (Baran Maskan, 2011; Partikasari Nurwita, 2019; Sahin Top, 2015) and teaching efficacy (Choi et al., 2019) following the implementation of a Project Based Learning process. There are indications that the Project-based Learning process positively affects the development of teachers' professional identity (Tsybulsky et al., 2020; Tsybulsky Muchnik-Rozanov, 2019) and their views regarding the teaching profession. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework and serves as the schemata of the study. In this study, two variables are illustrated. The first variable, which serves as the exogenous variable, is the digital text reading that contains an indicator, namely, motivation and interest in reading digital texts, digi-

tal texts reading efficacy, difficulty in reading digital texts, preference for reading digital or print texts while the endogenous variable in this study namely the reading comprehension with three corresponding indicators namely reading attitude, efficacy in instructional strategies and students' attitudes to the facilities and resources. Lastly, the study's mediating variable is the teachers' teaching efficacy, with three corresponding indicators: efficacy in student engagement, student engagement, and teacher satisfaction. Efficacy in instructional strategies and efficacy in classroom management. The first box serves as the study's independent variable, which is connected with an arrow pointing at the second, which mainly serves as the dependent variable. The box in the middle serves as the mediating factor that connects the independent variable to the dependent variable. The arrow serves as an indication that the first variable, the digital text reading, has an impact on the reading comprehension of the students, which is the dependent variable

Meanwhile, the independent variable, digital text reading, also points an arrow at the mediating variable, which affects teaching efficacy. On the other hand, it also points to the student's reading comprehension, which denotes the reading-dependent variable.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study aims to evaluate the role of digital text reading and the student's reading comprehension as mediated by the teachers' teaching efficacy. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of digital text reading in terms of:
 - (1) Motivation and Interest
 - (2) Efficacy
 - (3) Difficulty; and
 - (4) Preference for Reading Digital or Print Texts?
- (2) What is the extent of reading comprehension in terms of:
 - (1) Reading attitude
 - (2) Instructional Strategies; and
 - (3) 2Students' attitudes to the facilities and resources?
- (3) What is the extent of teaching efficacy of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) Efficacy in Student Engagement
 - (2) Efficacy in Instructional Strategies; and
 - (3) Efficacy in Classroom Management?
- (4) Is there a significant relationship between:
 - (1) Digital Text Reading and reading comprehension of the students?
 - (2) Teaching efficacy of teachers and reading comprehension of the students?
 - (3) Digital text reading and teaching?
- (5) Does the teachers' teaching efficacy significantly mediate the relationship between digital text reading and students' reading comprehension?

1.5. Hypothesis—The hypothesis was tested at $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance. The following hypotheses were drawn to determine if there is a level of significance, a significant difference, and a relationship among the variables, the following hypothesis were drawn as follows: Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the digital text reading and the reading comprehension of the students Ho2: There is no significant relationship between teaching efficacy and students' reading comprehension. Ho3: There is no significant relationship between Digital text reading and teaching Ho4: Teaching efficacy does not significantly mediate between digital text reading and students' reading comprehension. Additionally, examining the individual characteristics of the different variables

will shed light on the unique factors that influence the students' reading comprehension, ultimately aiding in the design of targeted interventions to promote academic success. Public and Private Teachers The study's results assist educators in recognizing their pupils' reading comprehension difficulties and creating effective lesson plans to address those issues. Teachers can also learn helpful teaching techniques and tactics from this research to encourage their students to read more digital texts and to be more motivated to improve their reading comprehension. School Administrators School administrators can gain essential insights from this study regarding teacher professional development in creating teaching strategies and refining student learning styles, particularly concerning

the emergence of solid student comprehension in their respective schools. The study's results can assist educators in determining the areas in which their pupils are weak and create programs and interventions to help them become more proficient readers. Department of Education Policymakers can use the study's findings to understand better the variables impacting teachers' approaches to teaching students and to create targeted interventions to enhance these areas. Through the research, policymakers can learn how to ensure an effective instructional process by improving the quality of teaching tactics.

Future Researchers Future researchers who wish to learn more about the elements influencing students' reading comprehension, the usage of digital text reading, and the effectiveness of instructors' instruction may find this study a helpful resource and starting point. The following terms would be operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive.

Digital Text Reading

Refers to an act of reading text that is produced using digital or electronic technology. Digital texts, including animations and hyperlinks, can be audio, visual, or multimodal. Examples of digital texts include websites, movies, e-books, and apps.

Comprehension of Students

Refers to Comprehension, which is the ability to understand the meaning of written words. It is the ultimate goal of reading. It is more than just recognizing words; it involves turning words into thoughts and ideas.

Teacher Efficacy

Reflects a teacher's confidence in their ability to help students learn and succeed. It is a valuable asset for teachers and is linked to many positive outcomes, including student outcomes, such as achievement, motivation, and self-efficacy beliefs, and teacher outcomes, such as persistence, enthusiasm, commitment, and instructional behavior.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work meticulously during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a correlational research design to determine the variables' associations. A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating them. According to Bhandari (2023), a correlation reflects the strength or direction of the relationship between two or more variables. Correlational research

is ideal for gathering data quickly from natural settings. That helps you generalize your findings to real-life situations in an externally valid way. There are a few situations where correlational research is an appropriate choice. To investigate non-causal relationships, they want to find out if there is an association between two variables, but they do not expect to find a causal relationship between them. This study could

serve as a basis for higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where learners could benefit. The researcher considers social value an important criterion for ethical research. It is the expected benefit that a research intervention would bring to the well-being of society or patients. Ethical considerations in research are important for protecting the rights and welfare of research participants. Some ethical issues in research include anonymity, not collecting personally identifiable data, and keeping participants' identities hidden.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety

The researcher may fully disclose the nature of the study to the respondents, explaining its purpose, benefits, and the confidentiality of their responses as outlined in the survey. Respondents may be free to ask any questions about the study, and the researcher would ensure no harm. The questionnaire and interview guide were designed to avoid offensive or inappropriate content. The study may focus solely on academic information, with no personal data being requested. Respondents may have ample time to complete the survey online. They were free to skip any questions that may cause psychological or emotional distress or withdraw from the study at any point. The researcher prioritized their well-being and valued their participation. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents are provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members if they have queries related to the study. This was done to answer the respondents' possible questions. Furthermore, if respondents experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they was not be compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire is distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study is

the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Justice To ensure fairness in selecting respondents, the researcher would treat all participants equally, without bias. Eligible respondents will be chosen based on their qualifications as permanent regular teachers in the selected schools. The researcher will also respect the respondents' time, minimizing disruptions to their daily routines. As a gesture of appreciation, tokens of gratitude, such as souvenirs, will be sent to respondents via courier, with each package carefully sealed and sanitized. The research ensures that the respondents was informed of my role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to answer the survey questions honestly and that any communication related to the research should be honest. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency To protect participants' welfare, all communications related to the study will be conducted honestly and transparently. The researcher will properly implement all methods discussed in the study. Additionally, the necessary documents supporting data analysis will be included. The researcher will clearly outline the extent of the respondents' involvement and ensure objectivity in analyzing and presenting the study's results. The respondents and parents of the participating schools can access the study's results because the information is available and was placed on a CD, which can be requested from me anytime. In addition, by learning about the study's results, parents and learners will be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-

being. Further, each participant is advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This may allow the participants to amend or remove any information that might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study's population may consist of elementary schools chosen from the division. These populations are involved based on their interest in improving the quality of education by adhering to the primary purpose and objectives of the study. The respondents are the Laak North District, the Division of Davao de Oro students. The researchers would consider 169 out of 300 bonafide students enrolled in Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro schools as study respondents by the used of Roasoft Calculator. According to Thomas (2022) and Foley (2018), total population sampling was a sampling technique that involves examining the entire population. However, statistical studies generally use a sample, which is a subset of the population. In the case of total population sampling, the units of interest tend to have some characteristics that are not very common. It was important to note that only some characteristics were not very common. However, since these characteristics are what we are interested in, they influence our choice of total population sampling. Moreover, they added that total population sampling was a purposive method in which you examine the entire populace for just a set of characteristics. In these circumstances, the total population was often chosen because the crowd with the precise location of the desired qualities was so limited.

2.3. Research Instruments—A survey questionnaire employed in this study would

be adapted from the previous study and modified to suit a specific study's needs or context. This can involve adding, removing, or changing the content of questions. Moreover, the researcher used three sets of instruments in this study to ensure that the appropriateness of the study was adequately addressed. The questionnaire for the independent variable, digital text reading, is adapted and modified from the analysis of Researcher-made survey questionnaires from Sulaiman et al. (2021) for digital text reading, Wonglao (2022) for English Reading Comprehension, and Emiru and Gedifew (2021) for Teacher Self-efficacy. It will undergo validation from the expert and pilot testing to establish the survey instrument's reliability and validity. The pilot testing would identify at least 30 respondents for the said purpose. The researcher modified and changed it to fit the demands of the population, and the study's objectives serve as the study's instrument. Using a survey questionnaire is appropriate for this study since it allows the researcher to quickly get a large amount of data. Additionally, by modifying and altering the questionnaire, the researcher can tailor the survey questions to be more relevant and tailored to the study's objectives and the population under inquiry. Professionals in the field of education evaluated the questionnaire employed in this study. After that, a pilot test was conducted to assess its validity and reliability. The reliability of the original scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.761. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents was use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of digital text reading, students' reading comprehension, and teacher efficacy. The researcher made use of a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below: The survey used in this study employed a 5-point Likert scale. A Likert scale is widely used in the social sciences, particularly in educational research, to gauge people's attitudes, opinions, and perceptions

regarding a specific subject. Respondents can rate topics on a five-point Likert scale, which goes from strongly agree to disagree strongly, to indicate how much they agree or disagree with a statement. This measure is extensively used in research. Using a 5-point Likert scale in this study makes sense since it provides a range of

responses that can capture minute variations in the respondents' opinions or beliefs. The final copy were validated by the panel of experts for approval, and the final revision would incorporate the corrections, comments, and suggestions given by the experts before distribution and administration.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The digital text reading of the students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The digital text reading of the students is very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The digital text reading of the students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The digital text reading of the students is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The digital text reading of the students is never manifested.

For the independent variable, the teaching strategies, a modified and adapted questionnaire from Sulaiman, Ambarwati, and Syahri (2021)

with 20-item questions, will be used to assess the extent of the students' digital text reading.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The reading comprehension of students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The reading comprehension of students is very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The reading comprehension of students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The reading comprehension of students is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The reading comprehension of students is never manifested.

For the dependent variable, students' reading comprehension, a modified and adapted questionnaire from Wonglao (2022) was altered to 16-item questions. The Likert Scale above will be used to assess students' reading comprehension. For the mediating variable, the teach-

ers' teaching efficacy, a modified and adapted questionnaire from Sulaiman, Ambarwati, and Syahri (2021) for digital text reading was used, while Wonglao (2022) had 25-item questions. The Likert Scale below would assess the teachers' teaching efficacy.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teaching efficacy of the teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teaching efficacy of the teachers is very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teaching efficacy of the teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teaching efficacy of the teachers is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teaching efficacy of the teachers is never manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The data may be collected using the following process: The researcher may request approval from the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study. A formal letter and the Dean’s endorsement would be forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent for permission. The researcher would also seek authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Laak North District to survey the teachers. Once the Schools Division Superintendent grants permission, the approval letter will be presented to the principals and supervisors of public schools in the Laak North District to arrange the study. The researcher may coordinate with the school principals and supervisors while adhering to safety protocols throughout the research process. The researcher may distribute the survey tool and collect the responses upon approval. Ethical standards and protocols were strictly followed, and the data and participants were handled confidentially. The principals may keep a copy of the approval letter as proof that the data collection was conducted honestly and transparently. The gathered data would be tallied, tabulated,

analyzed, and interpreted confidentially. The study’s results would be analyzed in line with its purpose. After the data was collected and organized, it was sent to a statistician for further analysis. Respondents from the Laak North District would participate voluntarily, with the option to withdraw from the study at any time without facing consequences. Respondents provided personal and professional information as required, and all data was treated confidentially. The research questionnaire was written in clear, simple language to avoid technical jargon and prevent bias. No survey questionnaires were distributed without permission from the appropriate authorities.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean and Standard Deviation

This may identify the level of Digital Text Reading, teachers’ Teaching efficacy, and students’ reading comprehension.

Pearson r- r-correlation

May be used to identify the significant relationship between the variables. Multiple regression may be used to identify the relation between one dependent variable and multiple independent variables.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of learners’ learning preferences, classroom engagement, and information communication strategies; the significant relationship among the variables; and the mediating effect of information communication strategies on the relationship between learning preferences and classroom engagement of learners in Laak North

District, Division of Davao de Oro students.

Digital Texts in terms of Motivation and Interest Table 1 shows the results of Reading Digital Texts regarding Motivation and Interest. In particular, this indicator has a category mean of 3.73, interpreted as extensive, which means that in terms of Motivation and Interest, the learning preferences of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro students are oftentimes observed. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.38 to 4.16. The item, 1. Reading digital texts is motivating, reflecting a mean rating of 3.38, which is moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed among learners. Meanwhile, the item, the features of digital texts make them exciting to read, shows a mean rating of 4.16, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the respondents. The result suggests that respondents oftentimes take Reading Digital Texts in terms of their alignment with their Motivation

and Interest. The finding is in consonance with Motivation and interest. Baier, cited in Manalu (2020), pointed out that reading comprehension is important in all subject areas. Additionally, Pardede (2017) accentuated that reading is the most vital skill every EFL learner should master for several reasons. First, EFL learners study English in an environment where English is not the primary language of society. Their lack of input from their daily interactions could best be overcome through reading. Secondly, numerous studies have shown the important contribution of reading to one’s personal and intellectual development, further studies, job success, and career development. Third, reading skills increase a learner’s mastery of other language learning areas. Finally, reading advances writing skills, allowing the learners to figure out how to express ideas through words, use punctuation correctly, and so on.

Table 1. The Extent of Reading Digital Texts Regarding Motivation and Interest

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Reading digital texts is motivating.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
2. More interested in reading digital than printed texts.	3.92	Extensive
3. Feel comfortable when studying or reading using digital text.	3.79	Extensive
4. The features of digital texts make them exciting to read.	4.16	Extensive
5. Digital reading emerges as a positive experience; one often learns and does assignments using digital media.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.73	Extensive

Motivation has been argued as perhaps the second most significant factor in second and foreign language acquisition, ranked second only to learner needs. As early as 1959, Gardner and Lambert demonstrated that motivational variables significantly influenced foreign language acquisition (Lustyantie Aprilia, 2020). Guthrie et al., cited in Lustyantie and Aprilia (2020), concluded that motivation predicted reading comprehension growth, though the vice-versa

was invalid. Gender and ethnic differences impact learners’ reading motivation and, hence, reading comprehension. Yaghi (2019) found that when students independently read online materials, they are motivated by individual purposes, such as discovering new things or for pleasure. More recently, study that consonant to the results in Khatee (2020) that educators must first turn on student motivation when they want to improve students’ language achieve-

ment. When this motivation to learn a language has been provoked, it is hoped that they will persist in learning. Furthermore, achievement motivation is an individual factor that comes from within students, and good motivation in learning will show good results. This motivation boosts every student to achieve the highest possible goal. It is also a driving force to achieve maximum learning outcomes.

3.0.1. Reading Digital Texts in Terms of Efficacy—This indicator has a category mean of 3.59, which is described as extensive and interpreted as learning preferences among learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, which is oftentimes observed. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.12 to 4.11. The item, 2. Digital reading makes it easy to improve my comprehension, reflects a mean rating of 3.12, is described as moderately extensive, and is interpreted as sometimes observed. The items, 3. Learning through digital media increases achievement, with the same mean rating of 4.11, are described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed items. The results indicate that learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, often acquire new information by listening, repeating, or discussing ideas with others. This finding agrees with Research study of Bala, Prasad, Kasyap, Kumar, and Purushottam, (2023) has shown that technology-based approaches can effectively develop reading comprehension skills in engineering students. Digital tools, such as interactive reading apps and annotation tools, can also be effective in developing reading comprehension skills in engineering students. These tools allow students to engage with the text and provide feedback on their understanding.

]Reading Digital Texts in Terms of Difficulty

In particular, the domain on Difficulty reflects a mean of 3.61, interpreted as extensive,

Technology has a powerful impact on student engagement. It also serves as a tool for differentiation so that all students can succeed as learners in the classroom. Newsela is one platform that has gained attention as a potential tool for enhancing reading comprehension skills in various educational contexts. Newsela (2021) offers a variety of texts on various topics, including engineering, at different reading levels. These platforms can change the text's reading level, making the material more approachable and engaging based on the student's reading proficiency. Additionally, the platforms provide exercises and tests that might aid pupils in improving their reading comprehension abilities. According to a study by Pinal and Kshirsagar (2020), students' reading comprehension and speed were significantly increased when they used online reading platforms. Nguyen et al.'s (2019) research indicated that digital tools, like annotation tools, helped students' reading comprehension abilities. Various populations have been shown to benefit from technology-based techniques for increasing reading comprehension skills (Chen et al., 2019). These strategies increase student engagement and comprehension using digital technologies, including personalized learning experiences, multimedia texts, and interactive reading platforms. Additionally, they can give pupils immediate feedback, allowing them to monitor their development and find areas for development. Technology improves students' reading comprehension abilities. Technology fosters positive approaches to improving students' reading comprehension abilities. Technology always has a significant impact on pupils' reading abilities.

which means that students' Difficulties are often observed by the learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The mean ratings among the Difficulty aspects range from 2.25

Table 2. Reading Digital Texts in Terms of Efficacy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. I believe that learning with digital text is adequate.	3.22	Very Extensive
2. Digital reading makes it easy to improve my comprehension.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
3. Learning through digital media increases achievement.	4.11	Moderately Extensive
4. I can easily comprehend printed text.	3.85	Extensive
Mean	3.58	Extensive

to 3.66. The item, 3. The screen’s light soon hurts my eyes while reading digital text, which has a mean of 2.25, described as less extensive, which means that this particular item is seldom observed—notably, item 1. I have a problem getting information when reading through digital media. The mean rating of 3.17 is described as moderately extensive, meaning this item is oftentimes observed. This suggests that learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, sometimes learn best with an active, hands-on approach. This finding is by Makebo et al., (2022) and Tzivinikou, (2019) stress that the skill of reading is a highly complex process and holds a prominent position in scientific re-

search. It has been approached from various disciplines, such as cognitive psychology, linguistics, neuroscience, and educational science, both in theoretical and applied contexts. Reading fluency refers to reading accurately, quickly, and with appropriate expression and prosody. Although reading fluency is often associated with rapid and automatic word recognition, research indicates that this ability encompasses much more than simple decoding. Reading fluency is a critical factor in the development of reading skills and the improvement of reading comprehension. Many students with reading difficulties face difficulty effectively reading text (Whitney Ackerman, 2022)

Table 3. The Extent of Reading Digital Texts in Terms of Difficulty

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. I have a problem getting information when reading through digital media.	3.17	Moderately Extensive
2. Technical disruption from the computer decreases my reading motivation and comprehension.	3.15	Extensive
3. The screen’s light soon hurts my eyes while reading digital text.	2.25	Less Extensive
4. I always have the digital texts printed before reading it.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Mean	2.93	Moderately Extensive

They added that Proficient reading skills are essential for history and social studies. These subjects often require students to comprehend and analyze complex texts, understand historical events and concepts, and engage critically with social issues. Without strong reading abilities, students may struggle to grasp the content, make connections, and effectively participate in

classroom discussions. Developing proficient reading skills early on is crucial for students to succeed academically in history and social studies (Kaikoura Tzivinikou, 2023).

3.1. *The Extent of Reading Digital Texts in Terms of Preference for Reading Digital or Print Texts*—Correspondingly, the reading preference of the learners Digital or Print for Text

reveals a category mean of 3.07, described as moderately extensive, which means that this indicator is sometimes observed by the learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The item mean ratings are ranging from 2.87 to 3.21. The item, 1. I more often read digital than printed texts, which has a mean rating of 2.87 and is described as moderately extensive, which means that this particular item is oftentimes observed by the respondents, while item 2. I love searching the internet for relevant additional texts to study, which has a mean of 3.21, described as extensive, which means that

this particular item is oftentimes observed by the learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. As such, the result suggests that the learners sometimes favor learning with their hands by manipulating resources. The finding supports Pardede’s (2019) statement that studies comparing the efficacy of perusing printed texts versus digital texts have not yet reached a consensus. Previous studies demonstrated that reading printed text was preferable to reading digital text in terms of reading speed, accuracy, and comprehension, whereas other studies revealed insignificant differences.

Table 4. Preference for Reading Digital or Print Texts

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. I more often read digital than printed texts.	2.87	Moderately Extensive
2. I love searching the internet for relevant additional texts to study.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
3. I like keeping the required digital texts on my gadget to read anytime and anywhere.	2.95	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.01	Moderately Extensive

However, students’ experiences and knowledge of digital text should be related to their age to influence their perception of digital reading. Another study conducted by Prawira et al. (2020) reported that mood at the moment will affect their performance in evaluating online sources. Digital texts have gained popularity as a teaching and learning tool while relatively young and constantly evolving (Wu Chen, 2018).

3.2. *Summary of the Extent of Reading Digital Texts in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro*—Overall, results in Table 5 show learners’ extent of learning preferences in

Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, reflecting an overall mean of 3.29, described as moderately extensive. This means that the learning preferences of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, are sometimes observed. In addition, the table results show that learning preferences in terms of visuals acquired the highest mean score of 3.73, which is described as extensive and interpreted as often observed. Meanwhile, perceptual learning styles in individuals acquired the lowest mean score of 2.44, which is defined as less extensive and interpreted as seldom observed.

The moderately extensive rating on this variable suggests that learners sometimes like to learn through perceptual channels. This finding is similar to the study of Wadi et al. (2022),

who stress that digital text is malleable, and depending on the technology and software used, various attributes, such as size, font, color, and contrast, that determine how the content is pre-

Table 5. Summary on the Extent of Reading Digital Texts in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Motivation and Interest	3.73	Extensive
Efficacy	3.58	Extensive
Difficulty	2.93	Moderately Extensive
Preference for Reading Digital or Print Texts	3.01	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.29	Moderately Extensive

sented to users can be changed to meet the needs of learners. Reading software compatible with text-to-speech can provide audio and visual components and other supporting structures separately and simultaneously, such as highlighting, dictionaries, and thesaurus. According to Kumar and Vijay (2023), teachers face challenges integrating digital technology into their instruction due to a lack of infrastructure, training, and high costs. Reading digital textbooks is reading the texts from technological apparatus such as the screen of smartphones, tablets, or computers, either online or offline. Unfortunately, the habits of digital text reading perceived by the students are still low due to external influencing factors, including computers, videos, games, and so forth era (Wadi et al., 2022). Clinton (2019) identified digital reading as reading a text from a device’s screen. These texts can be accessed from various devices, such as e-readers, computers, and smartphones. A single device gives readers access to a large number of books. These features give digital reading more convenience than paper in terms of accessibility and feasibility.

3.2.1. Comprehension Of Students In Terms of Reading Attitude—This indicator has a category mean of 3.82, which is described as extensive and interpreted as Comprehension of Students in terms of Reading attitude, which oftentimes manifests among the respondents. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.52 to 4.01. As the item, I find English reading comprehension in digital

text simple, reflects a mean rating of 3.52, is described as moderately extensive, and is interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the learners; similarly, item 2. I read additional materials (stories, magazines, etc., written in English) from class, which has a mean rating of 3.93, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Lastly, in item 3, I use English-English dictionaries described as extensive and construed as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents. Results imply that the majority of the students oftentimes go through the work for class, and they make sure that things are right by trying to understand their mistakes. This finding is congruent with the view of Reading attitude. Attitudes toward reading are primarily shaped by learners’ psychological states and emotions (Smith and Li, 2020). These attitudes can be defined as predispositions to respond consistently positively or negatively toward a specific object. A learner’s attitude may shift due to various factors, including environmental influences, prevailing conditions, personal interests, and the motivational impact of peers, as well as the individual’s current emotional state. In this context, the “object” may refer to an item, process, or behavior that directly or indirectly affects a learner’s attitude based on their personal experiences, beliefs, and societal norms related to that object. Reading attitude falls within the affective domain, encompassing feelings, thoughts, beliefs, and intentions. Together, these elements form the foundation of meaning (Akhmetova,

Imambayeva, and Csapó, 2022). It is widely believed that regular reading activities can positively impact reading attitudes and motivation and a favorable attitude toward reading will likely enhance future reading achievement. Research has indicated (Akhmetova, Imambayeva, and Csapó, 2022) that primary school learners generally exhibit a positive attitude toward recreational and academic reading. However, this positivity diminishes significantly as students transition to middle secondary school, highlighting a critical shift in their attitudes toward reading. Furthermore, researchers Akhmetova, Imambayeva, and Csapó (2022) suggest that reading for pleasure can foster a positive attitude toward reading, particularly within an effective classroom environment and with suitable instructional strategies. As such, the role of teachers in providing thoughtful instruction and adept scaffolding is crucial, as is the encouragement from parents and peers, both in and out of school. However, achieving this requires considerable collaboration and commitment from teachers, parents, and other stakeholders. There

are many discussions about whether reading attitude affects reading achievement or whether it is mostly the other way around. Some researchers assume that if the relationship between reading attitude and reading achievement is moderate and/or weak, this is not because of students' negative feelings towards reading but because of a lack of practice and poor abilities in reading, which cause difficulties in achievement. However, other researchers (Mullis, 2019) claim that a positive attitude toward reading could affect high achievement in reading, while other researchers (Graham et al., cited in Akhmetova, Imambayeva, and Csapó, 2022) maintain that reading attitude is primarily influenced by reading achievement. Hence, reading attitude and reading achievement could impact each other in the reading process. In addition, these findings agree with Hlalele's (2018) previous findings, who concluded that cognitive engagement is crucial in the classroom because engaged students are more likely to learn, find the experience rewarding, and continue with higher education.

Table 6. The Extent of Comprehension of Students in Terms of Reading Attitude

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. I find English reading comprehension in digital text simple.	3.52	Extensive
2. I read additional materials (stories, magazines, etc., written in English) from class.	3.93	Extensive
3. I use English-English dictionaries.	4.01	Extensive
Mean	3.82	Extensive

3.2.2. *Reading Comprehension in Terms Efficacy in Instructional Strategies* —This indicator has a category mean of 3.67, which is described as extensive and interpreted as classroom engagement in terms of behavioral engagement, which the learners oftentimes manifest. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.21 to 4.01. The item I can give a title to is a reading passage, with

a mean rating of 3.21. It is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested among learners. The item, Staying focused, has a mean rating of 4.01, defined as extensive and construed as an item oftentimes manifested among learners. This can be explained as instructional efficacy, encompassing teachers' belief in their competence to select and apply impactful teaching techniques.

Table 7. The Extent of Classroom Engagement in Terms of Efficacy in Instructional Strategies

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Before starting to read, I try to guess what the text will be about.	3.89	Extensive
2. I can scan a large text to get an overall idea.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
3. While I am reading, I can find out the main topic idea of a text.	3.88	Extensive
4. I can find out specific information from the text quickly.	3.88	Extensive
5. I can analyze long sentences and phrases.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
6. I can give a title to a reading passage.	4.01	Extensive
7. After finishing reading, I can summarize a reading text.	4.00	Extensive
8. I can distinguish the main ideas from supporting details.	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.67	Extensive

This confidence is vital as it significantly influences student involvement, educational achievements, and overall classroom effectiveness. Educators with strong efficacy tend to employ engaging strategies that cultivate a positive learning atmosphere and inspire students to strive for tremendous success, especially when faced with difficulties. The results suggest that the learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, often manifest participation, effort, attention, persistence, positive conduct, and the absence of disruptive behavior during class. This finding is similar to the conclusion made by Mohammed (2021), who tried to find out the strategies used to boost the speaking skills used in online learning by Saudi EFL students at the University of Bisha. The study found a promising result that students use strategies to learn language skills through different language learning strategies. Conversely, Zarei and Naghdi (2017) investigated the possible differences among self-efficacy as the outcomes of EFL learners' achievements. The study's findings indicated that students have positive results regarding self-efficacy, which was noted from the students' achievements. Similarly, Poulisse cited Mohammed and Mohammed (2022), who explored the impacts of compensatory strategies used to determine lexical problems of EFL

learners' comprehension levels. The impact of task-related issues on compensatory strategies was also tested. The study's sample is Dutch students, covering three different comprehension levels of students studying English. The study revealed that the comprehension level is in reverse to the total number of compensatory strategies.

]The Extent of Reading Comprehension In terms of Students' Attitudes To The Facilities and Resources

Specifically, examining the domain of Reading Comprehension, results in Table 10 reveal that its category mean is 3.39, described as moderately extensive, which means that this particular domain of classroom engagement of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, is sometimes manifested. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 2.98 to 3.71. Notably, "the library resources and services at the school are sufficiently available" has a mean rating of 2.98. It is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested by learners. Meanwhile, the item "classrooms are provided with IT facilities" has a mean rating of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 8. The Extent of Reading Comprehension in Terms of Students’ Attitudes to the Facilities and Resources

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. The library resources and services at the school are sufficiently available.	2.98	Moderately Extensive
2. The Internet is always accessible.	3.51	Extensive
3. Classrooms are provided with IT facilities.	3.67	Extensive
4. There is an acceptable number of students in each classroom.	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.40	Extensive

This finding is similar to the conclusion made by Fredricks et al. (2016) that students who form positive relationships with others are also more likely to have high academic achievement. Positive learning experiences, supportive relationships with adults and peers, and reaffirmations of their developmental needs in learning contexts make students more likely to remain actively engaged in school.

3.3. *The Summary of the Extent of Learners’ Reading Comprehension* —Lastly, Table

Table 9. Summarizes the Extent of Learners’ Reading Comprehension

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Reading attitude	3.82	Extensive
Efficacy in Instructional Strategies	3.67	Extensive
Students’ attitudes to the facilities and resources	3.40	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.52	Extensive

The result suggests that the level of engagement students exhibit in reading comprehension is crucial to their overall academic success. Actively participating in the learning process not only aids in information retention and developing critical thinking skills but also paves the way for a deeper understanding of concepts. When fully engaged, students demonstrate a keen interest in the subject matter, leading to higher levels of motivation and a more profound grasp of the material. Engaged learners do not just passively consume content; they actively

9 Summary of the Extent of reading comprehension. The overall mean of the classroom engagement of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, is 3.52, which is described as extensive. The results range from the highest, 3.82, to the lowest, 3.40. Reading Attitude with a mean rating of 3.82, Efficacy in Instructional Strategies, 3.67, and Students’ Attitudes to the Facilities and Resources, 3.40.

seek to decipher complex ideas, investing intellectual effort and taking ownership of their learning journey. Reading comprehension is an essential skill for navigating the textual world around us. It is a dynamic process that involves making predictions, summarizing the main idea, questioning one’s predictions, and clarifying unclear concepts. Building a logical mental picture of the content in a text is necessary for reading comprehension. Three interconnected components make up reading: the reader, the text, and the action, all of which are placed

within a larger sociocultural framework. The intricacy of reading comprehension has led to the development of numerous significant models and frameworks that try to explain the processes that result in reading comprehension, such as integrating newly acquired information with the contents of active memory and the activation of existing knowledge. Other models and frameworks try to consider the elements of language comprehension, vocabulary, and decoding that go into reading comprehension (Butterfuss et al., 2020).

3.3.1. *Teacher Teaching Efficacy in terms of Efficacy in Student Engagement*—Table 10 shows the extent of efficacy in Student Engagement, which reflects an overall mean of 3.53, described as extensive and interpreted as manifested oftentimes. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.34 to 3.71. The item “The teacher can motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork” reflects a mean rating of

3.34, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as information communication strategies of learners is sometimes evident. Meanwhile, the item “The teacher can motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork,,” has a mean rating of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident among learners. The result suggests that the Extent of Teacher Teaching Efficacy in terms of Efficacy in Student Engagement in a manner of Teaching efficacy, particularly in relation to student engagement, is crucial because a teacher’s belief in their ability to effectively engage students directly impacts the level of participation, motivation, and learning outcomes within the classroom; essentially, when a teacher feels confident in their capacity to capture students’ interest and involvement, they are more likely to implement strategies that foster active learning and positive student experiences, leading to better academic results.

Table 10. The Extent of Teacher Teaching Efficacy in Terms of Efficacy in Student Engagement

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. The teacher can help students think critically.	3.69	Extensive
2. The teacher can get through to the most challenging students.	3.54	Extensive
3. The teacher can motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork.	3.71	Moderately Extensive
4. The teacher can get students to believe they can do well in school work.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
5. The teacher can help students value learning.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
6. The teacher can foster student creativity.	3.50	Extensive
7. The teacher can improve the understanding of a failing student.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
8. The teacher can assist families in helping their children do well in school.	3.34	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.49	Extensive

The finding aligns with the view of Thien and Chan (2020) that teacher self-efficacy influences students’ engagement in learning. It is a multidimensional construct that includes efficacy in instruction, like the capacity to use

various instructional methods; classroom management, like the belief in maintaining classroom order; and student engagement, like the belief in motivating and engaging students in learning (Liu et al., 2020) Moreover, Havik and

Westergård (2020) demonstrate that teachers who provide high-quality classroom interactions, such as caring and supportive behavior and a structured classroom, foster high student engagement in learning. Teacher efficacy is believed to be influential in increasing academic success and motivation and has been revealed to significantly affect teachers' confidence in their teaching and instructional techniques (Rezaian Abdollahzadeh, 2020). The dimensions of teacher efficacy are efficacy in student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. This is one of the teacher factors that would significantly contribute to students' academic success. Therefore, teacher efficacy implies effectiveness in teaching and instructional practices (Goksu et al., 2022).

3.4. The Extent of Teachers Teaching Efficacy in Instructional Strategies —Table 11 shows the extent of teachers' teaching efficacy in instructional strategies, which reflects an overall mean of 3.53, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.34 to 3.73. The item “The teacher can gauge student comprehension of what you have taught” reflects a

mean rating of 3.34, which is moderately extensive and interpreted as information communication strategies of learners, which is sometimes evident. Meanwhile, “The teacher can provide appropriate challenges for competent students” shows a mean rating of 3.73, described as extensive and interpreted as often evident among learners in the North Laak District Division of Davao De Oro. The findings highlight the importance of a teacher's confidence in their instructional strategies, as it directly influences their ability to implement diverse teaching methods effectively. This leads to enhanced lesson planning, increased adaptability to student needs, and improved student outcomes. When teachers believe in their capacity to utilize various strategies, they are more likely to engage students actively and cultivate a positive learning atmosphere. Instructional strategies refer to the range of techniques teachers employ to facilitate student learning and comprehension of course material. These strategies enhance the learning process by making it more engaging and practical and empower students to play a more active role in their education.

Table 11. The Extent of Teachers' Teaching Efficacy in Instructional Strategies

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. The teacher can respond to difficult questions from your students.	3.54	Extensive
2. The teacher can gauge student comprehension of what you have taught.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
3. The teacher can craft good questions for your students.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
4. The teacher can adjust lessons to the proper level for individual students.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
5. The teacher can use a variety of assessment strategies.	3.50	Extensive
6. The teacher can provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
7. The teacher can implement alternative strategies in the classroom.	3.71	Extensive
8. The teacher can provide appropriate challenges for competent students.	3.73	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.49	Extensive

The finding agrees with (Bilali, 2013), as cited in Khalid and Akhter (2021). Teacher efficacy regarding instructional strategies relates to their confidence in engaging and creative teaching methods that enhance student learning. The ability of teachers to effectively engage students in the classroom is closely tied to their self-confidence, influencing their capacity to promote effective learning. Effective classroom instruction is demonstrated by teachers' skills in organizing, designing, and implementing curricula that yield positive results in conducive learning environments (Pas, Bradshaw, Hersfeldt, as cited in Khalid and Akhter, 2021). According to Pas et al. (as cited in Khalid and Akhter, 2021), practical education, proactive classroom management, and student involvement significantly contribute to teacher efficacy. Teachers with strong efficacy beliefs are more inclined to employ various motivational and instructional strategies that enhance student engagement, even in challenging learning contexts. In the current era of digital learning, it is essential for teachers to maintain high efficacy beliefs to foster commitment and persistence. Academic engagement refers to a student's level of involvement in their studies and their dedication and perseverance in learning. Increased student participation ultimately leads to improved academic achievement. Moreover, teacher self-efficacy is intricately linked to student self-efficacy; teachers with a robust sense of self-efficacy tend to promote a similar mindset in their students. Conversely, those with low self-efficacy can inadvertently foster a diminished sense of self-efficacy among their students. Educators with high self-efficacy possess in-depth knowledge of their subjects, are well-

This finding is similar to the conclusion made by a teacher's belief in their ability to positively influence student achievement, known as self-efficacy, which can significantly impact

prepared to meet student expectations, adopt diverse teaching methods to ensure student satisfaction, and continuously seek effective and engaging instructional strategies (Khalid Akhter, 2021).

3.4.1. Teachers Teaching in Terms of Efficacy in Classroom Management—This indicator has a category mean of 3.67, which is described as extensive and interpreted as classroom engagement in terms of behavioral engagement, which the learners oftentimes manifest. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.21 to 4.01. The item “The teacher can make expectations about student behavior clear” with a mean rating of 3.21. It is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested among learners. The item “The teacher can establish a classroom management system with each group of students” has a mean rating of 4.01, defined as extensive and construed as an item oftentimes manifested. The results suggest that a teacher's self-efficacy in classroom management plays a crucial role as it significantly influences their capacity to cultivate a positive learning atmosphere, handle student behavior with proficiency, and ultimately enhance student learning outcomes. Teachers who have confidence in their ability to manage a classroom are more inclined to employ effective strategies, resulting in improved student engagement and academic achievement. Effective classroom management demonstrates a teacher's versatile and top-tier skill set in establishing and upholding conducive rules for productive teacher-student and student-student communication, fostering cooperative student work, and successfully implementing optimal teaching methods.

various aspects of teaching. For example, teachers with high self-efficacy are more inclined to implement innovative teaching methods, effectively manage the classroom, deliver quality

Table 12. The Extent of Teachers’ Teaching Efficacy in Terms of Classroom Management

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. The teacher can control disruptive behavior in the classroom.	3.89	Extensive
2. The teacher can make expectations about student behavior clear.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
3. The teacher can establish routines to keep activities running smoothly.	3.88	Extensive
4. The teacher can get children to follow classroom rules.	3.88	Extensive
5. The teacher can calm a student who is disruptive or noisy.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
6. The teacher can establish a classroom management system with each group of students.	4.01	Extensive
7. The teacher can keep a few problem students from ruining an entire lesson.	4.00	Extensive
8. The teacher can respond to defiant students.	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.71	Extensive

instruction, empower students to take ownership of their learning, and cater to the needs of students with diverse abilities. Research also suggests that educators with advanced degrees exhibit greater efficacy in engaging students, highlighting the benefits of continuous professional development in enhancing teaching practices. Moreover, the capacity of a teacher to inspire students to participate actively in the learning process is widely recognized as a fundamental aspect of fostering student engagement (Shah, 2023). Classroom management encompasses a range of skills, characteristics, and ethical values that enable teachers to create a conducive and supportive learning environment for their students. All actions taken by teachers to promote an enriching educational setting are integral to effective classroom management (Djigic Stojiljkovic, as cited in Shah, 2023). According to Martin and Baldwin, as referenced in Shah (2023), there are three main approaches to classroom management: participatory, non-intervening, and collaborative. Teachers with strong professional ethics are better equipped to utilize effective classroom management strategies than those with low self-confidence (Godard et al., as cited in Shah, 2023). Educators

with a dedicated work ethic are likelier to implement structured, organized, student-centered practices and remain responsive to students’ input when implementing classroom management techniques. Teacher efficacy is crucial in enhancing the quality of education in every nation. Teachers with a strong sense of efficacy are more inclined to remain in the profession, dedicate more time to teaching, and invest more significant effort in effective classroom management. Myanmar, located in mainland Southeast Asia with a population of approximately 54 million, is experiencing a decline in educational standards. This decline can be attributed to inadequate teacher training programs and professional development opportunities.

3.5. *The Summary of the Extent of Teachers Teaching Efficacy*—Lastly, Table 13 summarizes the extent of teachers’ teaching efficacy. The overall mean of the classroom engagement of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, is 3.56, which is described as extensive. The results range from the highest, 3.71, in classroom management to the lowest, 3.41, which was shared by the two indicators of students’ engagement and instructional strategies.

Table 13. The Summary of the Extent of Teachers’ Teaching Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Student Engagement	3.49	Extensive
Instructional Strategies	3.49	Extensive
Classroom Management	3.71	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.56	Extensive

These results suggest that teacher efficacy is crucial as it directly influences a teacher’s confidence in their capacity to positively affect student learning. When teachers believe in their abilities, they are more motivated and resilient in facing challenges, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes. Essentially, a teacher with faith in their teaching skills is better equipped to create a positive learning environment and nurture student success. This result was similar to the study of Lauerma ten Hagen (2021). Teachers with higher levels of self-efficacy are more likely to persist in the face of difficulties or employ a broader range of teaching techniques, more precisely, which may be better suited to the specific and varied challenges they face in the classroom. A large body of empirical research has found that TSE is linked to a range of instructional outcomes, teacher instructional behavior, and teacher well-being, including student motivation, student engagement, student achievement, student self-efficacy, teacher work satisfaction, work commitment, teacher effectiveness, and instructional behavior’ (Mok Moore, 2019).

3.6. Relationship among Digital Text Reading, Reading Comprehension, and Teach-

ers Teaching Efficacy in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro —The results of the analysis of the relationship between digital text reading, reading comprehension, and teachers’ teaching efficacy in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship among the mentioned variables. Table 14 shows that reading comprehension has a significant positive relationship with the teacher’s teaching efficacy with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .660^{**}$, $p < .05$). This means the extent of reading comprehension and the teacher’s teaching efficacy are also significantly associated. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between reading comprehension and teacher teaching efficacy. The findings agree with Bosman and Schulze’s (2018) proposition that the preference to learn individually correlated most with motivation for achievement. Learners who performed well were significantly more inclined to learn individually than the low achievers.

Table 14. Relationship Among Digital Text Reading, Reading Comprehension, and Teachers’ Teaching Efficacy in Laak North District, Division of Davao Del Norte

Variables	Reading Comprehension (DV)	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Digital Text Reading (IV)	.492**	<.001	Reject Ho
Teachers’ Teaching Efficacy (MV)	.660**	<.001	Reject Ho

On the one hand, the result shows that the relationship between Digital Text Reading and reading comprehension in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro, has a significant positive relationship with a p-value of < 0.01 that is less than the alpha set at the .05 ($r = .492^{**}$ $p < 0.01$). This means that the extent of digital text-reading learners has a significant association. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between digital text reading and Reading Comprehension. On the other hand, there was a significant relationship between Teachers Teaching Efficacy (MV) and Reading Comprehension at the alpha .05. It can be concluded that there is an association between these variables. This means that every increase in the unit in each variable also affects the other unit of the other variable. The findings are congruent with Banditvilai's (2020) research, which found that reading strategies positively affected students' reading comprehension. The time to complete the task may also affect the study results, as stated in Martina, Syafradin, Rakhmanina, and Juwita's (2020) research, which revealed that time constraints affect the test of reading comprehension. Reading comprehension is crucial for students to learn from the writer's message and apply it to expand their knowledge and sharpen their intellectual faculties. Understanding the information the writer is trying to convey in a text is crucial. Based on the students' capabilities, they

eagerly hope to do the task that their teacher gives them. That is why it is necessary to know the influence of teacher teaching efficacy on the students in learning English, in this case, reading comprehension. Almost all teachers teach reading well. They must give their students strategies for comprehending the text and guide them to read it before asking them to answer the questions. As a result, the students tend to have high reading skills and habits for comprehending the text. This finding parallels the findings of a study conducted by students who must know the technique to understand the reading material easily and the rich vocabulary so they feel engaged when reading. Besides that, teachers must use background knowledge to activate their students' schemata about what they will learn. Thus, the teacher plays a significant role in developing the students' reading comprehension (Sinaga et al., 2019).

3.7. *Mediating Effect of Teaching Efficacy on the Relationship Between Digital Text Reading and Reading Comprehension*—Results in Table 15 show the mediating Teaching Efficacy on the Relationship Between Digital Text Reading and Reading Comprehension in the Laak North District Division of Davao De Oro. As shown in the table, Digital Text Reading is the independent variable of learners' Reading Comprehension, which is this study's dependent variable; the Sobel test was used to determine the significance of mediation.

Table 15. Mediating Effect of Teachers' Teaching Efficacy on the Relationship Between Digital Text and Reading Comprehension of Learners in Laak North District, Davao De Oro

Statistic	Z-test	P-value	Decision
Sobel test statistic	0.29361548	0.76905175	Accept

This study utilized the Sobel test to determine whether the Sobel test is a specialized t-test that provides a method to determine whether the reduction in the effect of the independent

variable, after including the mediator in the model, is significant and, therefore, whether the mediation effect is statistically significant. The result shows a z-test of 0.29361548 and a

p-value of 0.76905175, greater than the alpha of .05, and the z-test statistic is less than 1.96. The decision is to accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that the mediator variable (teachers' teaching efficacy) is not significantly mediating the digital text (independent variable and reading comprehension (dependent variable). The significant role of teachers' teaching efficacy as a mediator in the relationship between digital text reading and learners' reading comprehension is contributed to by the fact that there exists a relationship between these variables. It is emphasized in this study that teaching efficacy is an undeniable factor that has a positive relationship be-

tween digital text reading and learners' reading comprehension in the Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro. This finding agrees with Banditvilai's (2020) research, which found that reading strategies positively affected students' reading comprehension. The time to complete the task may also affect the study results, as stated in Martina, Syafryadin, Rakhmanina, and Juwita's (2020) research, which revealed that time constraints affect the test of reading comprehension. Reading comprehension is crucial for students to learn from the writer's message and apply it to expand their knowledge and sharpen their intellectual faculties.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The literature supports the discussions in the first chapters, and the conclusions are statements about the problem presented in this study. The study was intended to determine the mediating effect of teachers' teaching efficacy on the relationship between digital text and learners' reading comprehension utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-correlation technique. This study used path analysis through mediation to determine the mediating effect of teachers' teaching efficacy on the relationship between digital text and learners' reading comprehension. Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro students. The researcher considered all 300 bonified students enrolled in Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro schools as study respondents or samples. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: The extent of Digital Text Reading of learners in Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro has an overall mean of 3.29 and a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Regarding motivation and interest, Efficiency, difficulty, and preference for reading digital or print texts, the learners and the group obtained mean scores of 3.73, 3.58, 2.93, and 3.01, respectively. The extent of Reading Comprehension in Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro has an overall mean of 3.52 with a descriptive rating of

extensive. Also, learners' reading comprehension regarding Reading attitude, Efficacy in Instructional Strategies, and Students' attitudes toward the facilities and resources obtained mean scores of 3.82, 3.67, and 3.40, respectively. More so, the extent of reading comprehension in Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro has an overall mean of 3.52 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Finally, the teaching efficacy in terms of Student Engagement (3.49), Instructional Strategies (3.49), and Classroom Management (3.71). The result showed that teachers teaching efficacy has a significant pos-

itive relationship with reading comprehension in Laak North District Division of Davao de Oro with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .660^{**}$, $p < .05$). This means the extent of reading comprehension and the teacher's teaching efficacy are also significantly associated. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between reading comprehension and teacher teaching efficacy. Finally, Digital Text Reading has a significant positive relationship with the Reading Comprehension of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro, with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) .05 ($r = .492^{**}$ $p < 0.01$). Teaching efficacy does not mediate the relationship between Digital text reading and learners' reading comprehension in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro. The analysis was obtained from the Sobel test formula with a z-test of 0.29361548 and a p-value of 0.76905175. The decision was to accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, it was safe to conclude that the mediator variable (teachers' teaching efficacy) was not significantly mediating the digital text (independent variable and reading comprehension (dependent variable).

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as the survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions were generated: The Digital Text Reading in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro, was moderately extensive. Digital Text Reading, which deals with motivation, interest, and efficacy, acquired extensive ratings. Digital Text Reading is complex, and Preference for Reading Digital or Print Texts obtained moderately extensive ratings. This suggests that learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro, sometimes like to learn to embrace the new trends of learning development in the 21st century. The reading comprehension was extensive. Also, reading attitude and Efficacy in Instruc-

tional Strategies are descriptively rated as extensive. Meanwhile, students' attitudes toward the facilities and resources acquired a moderately extensive rating. This result suggests that students' level of engagement in reading comprehension is crucial to their overall academic success. Actively participating in the learning process not only aids in information retention and developing critical thinking skills but also paves the way for a deeper understanding of concepts. When fully engaged, students demonstrate a keen interest in the subject matter, leading to higher levels of motivation and a more profound grasp of the material. Engaged learners do not just passively consume content; they actively seek to decipher complex ideas, investing intellectual effort and taking ownership of their learning journey. The teachers' teaching efficacy in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro, was extensive. The indicators, such as student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management, are vast. These results suggest that teacher efficacy is crucial as it directly influences a teacher's confidence in their capacity to affect student learning positively. When teachers believe in their abilities, they are more motivated and resilient in facing challenges, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes. Essentially, a teacher with faith in their teaching skills is better equipped to create a positive learning environment and nurture student success, which is oftentimes evident among the respondents in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro. The result showed that teachers' teaching efficacy significantly correlates with digital text reading and reading comprehension in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro. Also, digital text reading was significantly associated with the learners' reading comprehension in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro. However, Teachers' teaching efficacy does not mediate the relationship between digital text reading and reading comprehension in Laak North District, Division

of Davao De Oro. This study emphasizes that teachers' teaching efficacy is an undeniable factor in the positive relationship between learning preferences and classroom engagement of learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro. In this study context, the overall findings on teachers' teaching efficacy do not mediate the relationship between digital text reading and reading comprehension in Laak North District, Division of Davao De Oro. However, some factors could be a reason, like indirect factors, and most of the students were engaged in social media and other forms of online applications. In contrast, these two variables were associated with each other based on the correlations and regression results. This study emphasizes that this study was guided by Hypertext Theory, as articulated by Hawkes, Murphy, and Law (2001), which delineates "hypertext" as a composition of word or image blocks electronically interconnected through various paths, chains, or trails. This description emphasizes a crucial attribute of hypertext: its capacity to connect conceptually distinct sections of a document or wholly separate texts. Unlike printed texts, which follow a strict sequence that readers must comply with, hypertext significantly increases readers' independence. This demonstrated the significance and efficacy of the variable in the current investigation. Conversely, reading comprehension encompasses social and emotional aspects, which is appropriate. Crawford (2020) regarded the theoretical framework as a component of the conceptual framework (CF) theory in research, especially in the social sciences, which explored the connections within the study to develop new theories or evaluate current ones. Thus, the theoretical framework offers the researcher a structured platform for articulating the research focus, progressing from the abstract to the study background, literature review, data collection, and analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings, evaluation of whether the study objectives and identified problems have

been addressed, summary, conclusion, and recommendations, as well as contributions to existing knowledge and suggestions for further research, with each component interconnected.

4.3. Recommendations—The researcher recommends that DepEd officials formulate policies that may improve educational practices regarding learners' classroom engagement. This policy will create quality standards for learning and teaching and set out expectations and accountability. Further, teachers may develop interventions that can be implemented regarding the importance of analyzing learners' own particular perceptual learning style preferences. These interventions can benefit the learners' classroom engagement and academic achievement by helping them become more focused and attentive. As shown in the study, teachers may continue their teaching efficacy. Furthermore, learners may continue to embrace their responsibility of improving themselves, especially in reading digital text, since their results are at a moderating level only. This will help them increase their capabilities and strength, enhancing the effectiveness of their learning experience. Furthermore, learners can improve their digital text-reading skills by utilizing digital books, including embedded tools such as text-to-speech, highlighting features, and glossaries. Encouraging active reading strategies—such as note-taking and summarizing—can further support comprehension. Incorporating graphic organizers helps visualize information while fostering discussions through reading groups promotes deeper engagement. Additionally, teaching students to navigate digital platforms effectively can minimize distractions. Ultimately, these strategies transform the reading experience into an interactive and engaging process while addressing potential challenges associated with digital text consumption. In addition, researchers may conduct further analysis on the factors that may contribute to the relationship between digital text reading and reading com-

prehension of learners since only 30.80 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable. The study's results may be published in reputable or prestigious publications.

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